

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES BY LECTURERS/SPECIALISTS OF DIFFERENT FIELDS OF STUDY- A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

General English is being taught with great success around the world from an early age. As this trend continues, students will leave primary and nine-year education with the traditional general English curriculum already completed, and regardless of how competent they have become in the language, they will not want to repeat the same things in high schools or even university systems – their English studies will need a purpose. English for Specific Purposes is being used and needed more and more by students, who find it indispensable in order to succeed in their future profession.

The importance of ESP has increased over the years. However, a new trend is being noticed recently; the use of ESP by lecturers of other subjects (other than English teachers).

A study was designed to test the level of ESP usage by specialists and professors of two different universities, University of Tirana and Polytechnic University of Tirana. The study was conducted to highlight their knowledge of ESP (even though they are not ESP lecturers), the circumstances in which these specialists have to use ESP, the reasons and the frequency students are given ESP materials to assimilate best and to enlarge more their knowledge and information about other subjects.

Keywords: ESP, general English, knowledge, profession, students, specialists, lecturers

1. Literature Review

Baldauf and Jernudd (1983) think that the increasing importance of English has inevitably developed in superiority over other languages, so that more than 90% of literature in some scientific fields is printed in English and also most books and the most prestigious and popular journals in various fields are in English. Countless students and academics around the world need to gain fluency in English-language academic discourse conferences to understand their disciplines, secure their careers, or successfully research their learning.

According to Orr (2010:213), science and engineering schools are constantly looking for better ways to improve the English language skills of their students, but English for Special Purposes (ESP) specialists, who have the right knowledge, skills and interests to contribute strongly in this direction, unfortunately do not have enough materials.

Harding (2007:6) has listed some of the factors that have influenced the increasing importance of ESP:

- Increased learning and professional qualification around the world. Students want their studies to lead them to something useful. Economy and trade want to employ people with professional skills.

- Globalization continues to spread and has openly chosen the English language as the language of communication, because English as the language of international communication is spreading faster and faster.

This language is influencing even people who thought they wouldn't need English before. We are not talking only about politicians, businessmen, academic professors, who need to communicate with their international colleagues and clients, but also about hotel receptionists, nurses, etc.

Belcher (2004:166) identifies the pragmatism of ESP, that is, the commitment to be responsive to the academic needs of the target language and the employability needs of students, as a central force in the given field. In this way, reading literature tends to focus on how it will be learned.

From this point of view, Bruce (2011:140) analyzes this situation in the following terms:

Reading is sometimes taught on its own as a separate skill, sometimes together with writing, and sometimes as a component of a study program.

Flowerdew and Peacock (2001:8), as well as Jordan (1997:1) write that English for academic purposes is usually defined as the teaching of English in order to contribute to and support students' studies or research aspects of that language.

Hyland (2008:113) reminds us that: "Needs analysis is like any other classroom practice because it involves decisions based on educators' interests, values, and beliefs about teaching, learning, and language."

According to Bocanegra - Valle (2010), this great dependence on "specialty" is the key feature that emphasizes the differences between teachers of English as a foreign language, English as a second language and as implementers of ESP as finders of materials.

Jack C. Richards and Thomas. S. C. Farrel (2005:3) identifies two broad types of goals within the field of teacher education, which are training and development.

2. Material and method

In order to concretize the importance of English for specific purposes, not only by ESP lecturers, but also by lecturers/specialists of different fields of study, a study was conducted about ESP use in different faculties of two universities (Polytechnic University of Tirana and University of Tirana, Albania).

A total of 106 lecturers participated in the study, including 57 lecturers from PUT (academic staff in the Faculty of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning, Faculty of Mathematical Engineering and Physical Engineering) and 49 lecturers from UT (academic staff at the Faculty of Economics, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Faculty of Social Sciences).

The survey consisted of 4 questions, each with four given alternatives, in which the lecturers had to circle only one alternative, the one used the most. In two of the questions included, the lecturers could add an answer based on personal experience under the alternative "other".

The purpose of this study was to highlight:

- Foreign language acquired during university studies by lecturers/specialists of various fields of study.
- The frequency of using ESP by lecturers/specialists of different fields of study.
- Acquisition of the lessons of other subjects by students, based on ESP materials given by lecturers of other subjects.
- The most frequent cases when lecturers or specialists from different fields must use ESP.

3. Foreign language acquired during university studies by lecturers/specialists of various fields of study

In order to highlight the foreign language that the surveyed academic staff has acquired during university studies, the chart is presented as follows:

Chart 1. Foreign language acquired during University Studies

Results and discussions

The data show that the majority of UT lecturers have acquired the general English language in the auditoriums of their university system (59.2% compared to 28.1% of PUT lecturers). It is noted that, in general, PUT lecturers have a variety of selections, in which the combination of general and specific English dominates (31.6%), compared to 12.2% of UT lecturers. Regarding the specific English language, it is noted that we have a selection of UT lecturers surveyed of 28.6%, compared to 17.5% of PUT lecturers. This apparent difference in favor of UT lecturers is well explained because a significant number of PUT lecturers circled the alternative "other" in which they added that they have acquired another foreign language or studied in counterpart universities abroad (22.8%). No answer has

been given by UT lecturers here. This is also explained by the fact that PUT students had the right to choose one of five foreign languages (English, French, Italian, German, Russian, from 5 years now Russian is replaced by Japanese) while at UT, only the English language is offered as a subject.

4. The frequency of using English for specific purposes by lecturers/specialists of different fields of study

Nowadays English language has taken large proportions in use. Yes, and what's more, English for specific purposes is gaining more and more importance. But the question naturally arises: "How often do lecturers of courses in different fields of study use ESP?"

Below is the chart with the corresponding results:

Chart 2. The frequency of using English for specific purposes by lecturers/specialists of different fields of study

Results and discussions

The survey highlighted once again the necessity of acquiring ESP. The lecturers of the two universities are unanimous in their choice, because they have to use English for specific purposes "often" or "always". A low percentage of lecturers have selected the alternative "sometimes" (PUT-7.0%; UP-10.2%). None of the 106 surveyed lecturers chose the "never" option. This shows that even though the academic staff has mastered subjects in the Albanian language, their preparation cannot be conceived without the use of ESP. Thus, it is clear that the difficulty of lecturers who have not studied English for specific purposes is much greater.

5. Acquisition of the lessons in other subjects by students, based on ESP materials

English for specific purposes, apart from the fact that it enables students to expand specific terminology and knowledge in the field of study, also helps them to have better opportunities to prepare more easily in other Albanian subjects. Most of the time, lecturers of these subjects suggest materials for students that should be assimilated in English and reproduced in their native language.

Below is the chart that shows whether the lecturers of the Albanian subjects give students the task to read ESP materials:

Chart 3. Students' acquisition of the Albanian subjects, based on ESP materials.

Results and discussions

In order to better meet the needs of the students and to better assimilate the knowledge and information given in the textbook of their subject, almost every lecturer uses supplementary materials which are used not only for their own preparation, but also for the students. These materials are mostly provided in English.

Nunan (1992:98) points out that experienced teachers find certain sort of materials more useful than others. It's important that the materials are authentic and this authenticity should relate to the text sources.

From the results of the chart, it was found out that lecturers of the two universities not only suggest students read materials in ESP, but many of them also consider it as a separate task. It is noticed that UT lecturers (22.4% - sometimes; 44.9% - often; 20.5% - always), apply this teaching method much more, which helps a lot in the acquisition of subjects in the field of study, compared to the lecturers of PUT (61.4% - sometimes; 26.3% - often; 7.0% - always). This is also explained by the fact that most UT lecturers were lecturers of social subjects, and the possibility of browsing and finding ESP materials in the field of study is much bigger.

At the same time, it is noticed that the number of UT lecturers who never give students the task of finding ESP materials to better assimilate the lessons of the relevant subject of the field of study is bigger compared to those of PUT (never UT-12.2%; PUT-5.3%).

Even if PUT lecturers do not ask students to read supplementary materials in English during the semester or academic year that covers their course, at the end of the course they must definitely suggest such materials, because PUT students are obliged to submit a course work in every subject.

6. The most frequent cases when lecturers or specialists from different fields must use ESP

Lecturers or specialists of different fields of study, as was ascertained from the chart above, *often* use ESP and many of them *always* use it. To highlight the cases in which they have to deal with ESP the most, four alternatives were given, one of which leaves room for lecturers to give any other alternative based on personal experience.

The chart below shows the corresponding results:

Chart 4. The most frequent cases when lecturers or specialists of different fields have to use ESP

Results and discussions

Unlike the other charts, it was almost unanimity observed the selection of alternatives given by the lecturers of the two universities. They use ESP mostly in their daily work to consult supplementary materials of the subject they cover (PUT-36.8%; UT-38.8%). Being in the dilemma of choosing between the suggested alternatives, the lecturers have chosen the other alternative (PUT-33.3%; UT- 32.7%), where they have also specified the case of use. It was highlighted that 32.7% of UT lecturers use ESP both for consulting materials, but also for participating in international conferences and preparing scientific articles in English, combined with the first alternative, i.e. communicating with foreign colleagues. While from 33.3% of PUT lecturers (19 lecturers in total), 13 lecturers have selected the first three alternatives, 1 lecturer the first and the second and 5 others the second and the third. The selection of the second alternative is mostly explained by the fact that to be a good lecturer, a systematic preparation must be carried out, while participation in conferences or publications and meetings with counterpart colleagues is not so frequent for the majority of lecturers.

PUT lecturers must also collaborate with foreign colleagues, and this is also reflected in the selection of the first alternative or the first alternative combined with other alternatives.

7. Conclusions

The use of ESP by lecturers/specialists of different fields of study of Albanian subjects is inevitable and necessary, regardless of the fact whether or not these lecturers have studied English for specific purposes as

a different subject during the educational system in their university.

The necessity of using ESP by lecturers is reflected in different situations, both in the consultation of supplementary materials that they cover, in participation in international conferences and in publications, as well as in communication with foreign counterpart colleagues. These lecturers not only use ESP for personal preparation, but also to enrich students with additional information related to the relevant lessons of the subjects of their field of study, and as a result students will feel more self-confident in the near future when they start their profession.

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